

Psychodynamics of Professional Challenges Among Female Leaders in Higher Educational Institutes: In Context of HEC Policies & Practices

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ABSTRACT: A mixed method Sequential design study has been conducted to highlight the Higher education Commission Policies which intricacies psychodynamic factors inherent in the professional hurdles faced by women leaders in institutions of higher learning Balochistan, Pakistan. In this very same context, refers to staging an intricate interaction of psychological variables influencing and UNS shaping women's leadership efforts at the academic front. The present study tries to capture some of the subtleties of psychodynamic factors influencing decision processes, interpersonal relations, and coping mechanisms through challenges that are gender-specific. The qualitative part of the research involves the assessment of 15 female leaders through in-depth interviews to gain insight into their psychosocial experiences. The present study tries to explore answers to questions about how personal convictions, motivational intent, and societal expectations dynamically interact with each other to influence leadership behavior, strategy, and outcome. Based on an explanatory sequential mixed method design, the quantitative phase involved 250 participants who completed a closed-ended, Likert-scale questionnaire that ensured a deep understanding of the psychosocial environment. All data were analyzed using SPSS. Because of this research, the gripping effects of the psychosocial and professional development challenges most female higher education leaders are facing have been brought to light. Hence, governments and institutional leaders should, therefore, recognize these factors and bring change in a hesitantly revised improved policy as they play a huge part in creating this habile environment, which has made life difficult for women to take leadership positions in institutions of learning.

Key words: Women, Academia, Leadership, Balochistan

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1. Introduction

In Pakistan's higher education institutions, both male and female leaders have increasingly participated in educational development and leadership roles. Notably, there has been a significant rise in the number of women occupying executive, managerial, and operational leadership positions between 2019 and 2020, marking a notable departure from

the previous five years. The change has remained a focal point of studies relating to higher education leadership [Elisado, 2022]. But even with this change, the number of leadership roles within the institutions is still not consistent for women. Cooper & Higgins, 2015. A large body of research investigated questions of educational leadership representation in terms of gender difference and especially if women were underrepresented in comparison to men due to differences in perceptions of the self as a leader or educator. These studies researched subtle interplay of factors that shape women's perception of self and experience. As Ahmad, Bakhsh, and Rasool emphasize 2019, it is very critical to empower male and female leaders in institutions of higher learning so that they can assist in creating an emotional attachment with peers and colleagues (Glatter, 2012). Institutions impart practical but also intangible insights on the subtleties of educational leadership. More than that, this is significant since the private and public sectors of higher education institutions of Pakistan have been riddled with the most divergent pressures-both internal and external-of educational leaders; hence, they have to be addressed. Without question, creativity is a leading leadership pillar that cannot be belittled as an imperative to organizational success (Ahmad, Bibi, & Imran, 2023). It lets them handle the complex systems governing their social and cultural environments by having an in-depth analysis of those systems. Besides, it equips them with the authority, in providing the right answers, effective approaches, and creative solutions to problems that face them directly in their workplaces Liu, Cutcher & Grant, 2015. With time, a number of studies have placed the progress of women towards leadership positions in higher education more firmly on the research agenda. For example, recent studies such as Robinson & Turner, 2018; Lee & Carter, 2021; White, 2022 represent just a few examples of how the issue has hugely drawn the attention of academics. These have illuminated some key issues, among them the underdevelopment of women for leadership in institutional higher learning environments, other external factors that affect their resilience, internal obstacles related to a university culture that serves as a ceiling for them making it to leadership, and the manifestation of stereotypes in leadership domains which expands the equality gap between men and women. Interestingly, more materials about the psychodynamic approach study of leadership have been observed in recent publications of research works. This tendency shows increasing interest in studying the psychological basis of leadership, and with it, there is an attempt to make clear the whole complex of individual and group interactions that have created effective patterns of leadership (Mohammad, et al., 2024).

Research Objective

- To evaluate the current policies and strategies of higher education commission to support women leadership in higher educational institutes in Baluchistan.

Research Question

- Are the current policies and strategies of HEC effective enough to support women leadership in higher educational institutes in Baluchistan?

2. Literature Review

The fact that women are greatly underrepresented in higher education leadership is a clear indication that the patriarchal leadership culture has highly prevented women from accessing such leadership positions. The small studies in the literature of academics with regard to leadership have been greatly conducted based on interpersonal relationships approximately by men and hence on the male leaders only (Ahmad & Dilshad, 2016). Consequently, the standards for assuming leadership positions have been shaped by male perspectives and traits (Biddle, 2017; Imran, Zaidi, & Rehan, 2024). Nonetheless, there is an emerging belief that many women exhibit leadership styles that align with effectiveness. Women leaders are often recognized for bringing about notable shifts in "interpersonal competence" approaches (Farah, 2013), encompassing skills like communication, emotional intelligence, teamwork, empathy, and adaptability.

However, research suggests that the organizational context significantly influences the perpetuation of traditional gender-biased leadership styles. In organizations with female leaders, women frequently assume leadership roles in tandem with male counterparts and are more inclined than men to adopt collaborative leadership styles. Research proves that these approaches can create a sense of comfort for employees, learners as well as boards who are accustomed to traditional male forms of leadership-Mukherjee, 2013. Another crucial matter to also pay attention to in order to realize gender parity at senior leadership level within institutions of higher learning is the equal representation of both men and women in leadership. In 2021, research in leadership conducted at Johns Hopkins University identified two reasons for the heightened gender leadership stereotypes in institutions of higher learning. These are the swastika of leadership attributes and personality and accessibility to the traditional and directive information regarding leadership opportunities. This research, while reinforcing some major points, has advanced further to advocate for more studies to be done that may influence professional development of female leaders working in the higher education environment. It also points to some alternative research methodologies and future directions for leadership studies.

Recent appointments in India and Pakistan are important milestones in higher education institutions' representation of women. Recent appointments, Aligarh Muslim University of India as a case in point with Professor Naima Khatun, and Government College University Pakistan appointing Dr. Shazia Bashir, have created history as vice-chancellors in these educational institutions are truly highly regarded. Both sets up about 150 years ago, have had a tradition of male leadership that raises pertinent questions about why it has taken so long for women to assume leadership roles in the academia. Dr. Mubarak Ali, who is a renowned historian in 2024, provides insight by showing the socio-cultural reasons that have led to this state of affairs especially given the gender based bias and institutional hindrances that were palpable in both countries. Dr. Ali explains that in spite of these gender parity steps at all levels, the deep-rooted prejudices remain because a place still exists for colleges and universities exclusive to women and limited scopes of Female education for females coming from relatively disadvantaged backgrounds. Dr. Ali also brought to light that just because a few posts have recently been assigned, it does not mean change has finally come. He also points out that the system has constantly

encountered challenges in eradicating gender-based disparities in education and society; therefore, these are efforts that need not stop.

3. Material and Methods

The qualitative segment of the study, labeled as part two, employed a semi-structured interview approach. This method was chosen due to its operational simplicity and flexibility during analysis. A key inclusion criterion for the 15 participants in this phase was their exclusive identity as women, a prerequisite for participation. Additionally, participants were required to hold senior positions within their respective higher education institutions. The interview questions were designed in an open-ended format to facilitate the generation of valuable insights. The researcher intentionally crafted these qualitative inquiries to closely align with the research objectives, maintaining a specific focus on the context of Balochistan province. The interviews explored significant variables, including challenges encountered by women leaders in higher education, opportunities available and pursued by them for technical reasons, as well as the societal and cultural influences on their employability in higher education. Furthermore, the interviews delved into topics such as the promotion pathways of women leaders to higher positions, their empowerment, sense of autonomy, and authority to practice their professions within a culture of collegiality and confidence.

For the quantitative section the researcher chose purposive sampling to enable the selection of individuals with distinct experiences and insights as women leaders in higher education. The respondents comprised Registrars, Heads of Departments (HoDs), Directors, Deans, and chairpersons. A total of 250 participants were targeted for inclusion in the study, with a sampling strategy that utilized a combination of probability and non-probability techniques in two stages, as outlined in the table provided.

4. Quantitative Results and Discussion

Need for Improvements

4.1. Improvements

The current policies and strategies regarding women leaders at government level need some improvement.

Figure No. 4.1 Improvements

The statement was answered by a total of n=250 samples. 27 samples expressed the strongest dislike, 60 expressed disapproval, 43 expressed neutrality, 52 expressed agreement with the message, and 68 expressed strong agreement.

The statement was answered by a total of n=250 samples. 23 samples expressed the strongest dislike, 40 expressed disapproval, 75 expressed neutrality, and 44 expressed agreement with the message, while 68 expressed strong agreement.

4.2. Gaps at Practical Level

Figure No. 4.2 Gaps at Practical Level

4.3. Need of Survey for Policy Amendments

Figure No. 4.3 Need of Survey for Policy Amendments

A total of n=250 samples responded to the statement. 29 samples strongly disliked the message, 40 showed disapproval, 43 stated indifference, and 70 agreed with it, while 68 strongly agreed.

4.4. Liberation of Institutions

Figure No. 4.4 Liberation of Institutions

The statement was answered by a total of n=250 samples. 23 samples expressed the strongest dislike, 34 expressed disapproval, 43 expressed neutrality, and 44 expressed agreement with the remark, while 106 expressed strong agreement.

A total of n=250 samples responded to the statement. 37 samples strongly disliked the remark, 46 indicated disagreement, 43 stated indifference, and 56 agreed with it, while 68 strongly agreed.

4.5. Focus on Supportive Strategies

Figure No. 4.5 Focus on Supportive Strategies

4.6. Supportive Environment

Figure No. 4.6 Supportive Environment

A total of n=250 samples responded to the statement. 37 samples strongly disagreed with the statement, 31 indicated disapproval, 70 showed neutrality, and 44 agreed, with 68 strongly agreeing.

4.7. Elimination of Glass Ceiling

Figure No. 4.7 Elimination of Glass Ceiling

A total of n=250 samples responded to the statement. 39 samples showed extreme dislike, 44 expressed disapproval, 43 stated neutrality, 56 expressed agreement, and 68 expressed strong agreement with the statement.

4.8. Policies for Work-Life Balance

Figure No. 4.8 Policies for Work-Life Balance

A total of n=250 samples responded to the statement. 49 samples strongly disliked the message, 32 indicated disagreement, 43 stated neutrality, and 44 agreed with it, while 82 strongly agreed.

5. Qualitative Results and Discussion

Their resilience was obvious not only in their readiness to tolerate uncertainty but also in their proactive investigation of new routes, so exemplifying a commitment to transcend established conventions and contribute to constructive change within the professional landscape.

5.1. Better Policies

The participants suggested that institutes should have better policies for women leaders to maintain a personal and family life.

Yes, definitely. Women do more than one work these days. If a woman is playing multiple role like doing her job and being a mother at the same time then some lenient policies should be made and implemented to balance work life and provide her with basic facilities.

Like if woman is playing multiple role, they must be shown support and assistance at all levels. If it is beyond optimal level, then you cannot help. Yes, I think institutes can have better policies and we should work on that.

5.2. Improvement in Existing Policies

The participants suggested that existing policies can be improved.

The policies are designed are human resourced, not based upon gender. So, there are many aspects to it. Human resource in terms of gender can be improved, and there are many loopholes in it. So, in the context of gender, different policies should be made for male and female.

Yes, at government level, but I do not see strong strategies

5.3. Amendments in Existing Policies

The participants suggested that existing policies should be amended.

Maybe there are policies to protect women, but intuitions are not supportive. What I mean is the judicial system and law and order who maintain is not supportive. The whole system is not supportive of female.

5.4. Liberation of Institutions

The participants recommended that the government should liberate the institutions further to customized polices and strategies.

I am not sure about this. At some places, institutions have customized policies. They might end up doing better than government institutions. If they are biased towards gender, it can also be negative. Government should not liberate institutions for separate policies or customized policies. Because women can go through worse policies and inappropriate environment which can affect them.

5.5. Training and Personal Growth

The participants recommended that there should be a separate institute for women leaders for training and personal growth.

Yes, this kind of institutes can be a very good option. When I attended a training on women, all the women were of almost same caliber. They can share their problems, they can give tips to each other and create sample space and trainees at similar place.

5.6. Institutional Support

The participant recommended that there should be some institutional support for women.

Women should be given a leadership position and support. They must not be discouraged.

5.7. Women should be Vocal

The participants suggested that women should be vocal.

Women must never compromise on their dignity. Material gains are not as important as much as a woman's self-esteem and her mental peace.

Secondly, women must learn to say no. Many women don't get confidence at home, or are deprived of learning environment, but even then they should learn where they should stand and say no if they are comfortable because many things can be beyond our comfort domain. If you have will, then only pursue your goal. These two things can bring huge change.

6. Conclusion

The ultimate investigation disclosed that the policies of the Higher Education Commission (HEC) were thought to be deficient in terms of equity and openness. Concerns were raised by participants regarding these policies' lack of consistency and coherence. Remarkably, the HEC was found to be the main cause of gender disparities in promotions. The study found that the HEC was the only organization that could be held accountable for creating an environment of inequity in the promotion procedures, underscoring the necessity of thorough reform and adherence to the values of justice and openness. This research on women's leadership in higher education underscores the pivotal role of professional support networks in facilitating career advancement, fostering meaningful experiences, and promoting success in educational leadership roles. Consistently, participants highlighted the significance of mentors, with several acknowledging the invaluable guidance received from executive coaches throughout their careers in educational leadership. The provision of executive coaching and mentorship emerged as indispensable resources in assisting these women in navigating the complexities of educational leadership, ultimately enhancing their career growth and accomplishments.

Recommendation

Based upon the findings the following recommendations are proposed,

- The head of the Institutions should highlight the gender based problems.
- The research revealed that the current state of policies within higher education institutions, aimed at offering women senior leadership opportunities and fostering the development of professional leadership capabilities, was deemed insufficient
- It is also recommended to the new researcher to do a further research this topic to explore the factors which are creating challenges.

- Specially designed training sessions should be offered before taking the leadership positions.
- The study identified that women in Balochistan and other education departments should depend on family support and social culture, emphasizing the importance of these factors in working diligently to attain senior leadership positions in higher education.
- To enhance the objectivity and effectiveness of leadership appointments, it is recommended that leadership positions be de-politicized, with political parties refraining from playing any role in the promotion or appointment process.

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